

Title: Deep Learning in Retail Analysis

Name: Anshuman Vikram Singh

Affiliation: AVSAK Labs

INTRODUCTION:

Deep Learning is being implemented in various AI applications from healthcare to agriculture. I have designed and developed many different tools using Deep Learning that can be used to perform customer analysis in retail stores based on their activity with certain products.

AIM:

To analyze the customer behavior towards products in retail stores.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A small camera has been built which will be mounted on the aisles of retail stores that will capture the live video stream and that video will be analyzed in real time.

RESULTS:

4 tools namely Expression Recognition, Face Tracking, Face Recognition and Appearance Recognition were built on different datasets. These tools gave state of the art results which will be beneficial for the retail stores for doing better customer analysis study.

CONCLUSIONS:

According to the results of this study, almost half of the crowns that were determined to have clinically acceptable margins had some sort of marginal discrepancy on radiologic evaluation.....

KEYWORDS:

Deep Learning, Retail Analysis, Expression Recognition

BIOGRAPHY:

Anshuman Vikram Singh has completed his MS in Computer Science from Rochester Institute of Technology, New York. He is the Co-founder and CEO of AVSAK Labs, a company which builds AI solutions. He has worked with various upcoming startups as a consultant and helped them build their products.